

Internet addiction

Mansour Mukhtar Ashkanani

Computer Department

High Institute for Administration Services

Public Authority for Applied Education and Training

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Abstract: Although Internet has great benefits, and greatly affected the world, especially in the field of scientific research, information dissemination, other than the many services it provides such as e-mail service, file transfer and sharing with others and many other benefits. Everything has its downsides, especially if we exaggerate in its use; the most obvious of these problems is Internet addiction.

Internet addiction is one of the newly emerging and striking problems, and it certainly has reasons behind this addiction, such as the great development in technology in addition to the ease of availability of the Internet, computers, mobile devices, and laptops, so the use of the Internet has increased rapidly. In addition, for some people have become the most important thing in their lives, it has become an addiction.

So in this research we will shed light on “Internet addiction” in terms of its causes, its negatives, the ethics and morals of the Internet, the ethical evaluation of Internet addiction, its symptoms, and in the end we present a vision for treating this problem.

Keywords: Internet, Addiction.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Internet and its various uses have become an integral part of our daily life. In addition, no one imagines the absence of the Internet in this world. To the extent that we can say: That it has become a daily habit, that reaches the point of addiction, and indeed Internet addiction has become a topic that grabs the attention of many, especially researchers and scholars. Moreover, indeed there is a lot of research and studies on “Internet Addiction” due to the importance and seriousness of this topic as well as the extent of its spread in all societies on his life in general.

Search problem:

The main objective of this field research is not only to know is there Internet addiction in Kuwait? However, we have to discuss the following points and answer these questions:

1. How addictive is the Internet in the State of Kuwait?
2. What is the age group that suffers from Internet addiction?
3. What are the main causes of Internet addiction?
4. What are the treatment methods?

Research methodology:

In order to achieve the objectives of this research, I will rely on the following scientific methods:

- a) The Deductive Approach: By studying and summarizing the researches that published before and related to the topic of the research. In addition, knowing the findings of these researches (the results) to start from where the others ended.

b) The inductive approach: Through the interpretation and analysis of the study according to the descriptive-analytical approach. Which based on the description of the phenomenon that I will carry out through the survey list that distributed to a sample of those who use the Internet in the State of Kuwait, in order to test the formulated hypotheses According to the objectives of the current study.

Research aims:

This research aims to reach the impact of Internet addiction on the individual and society, and try to find a treatment for this problem, because if we leave this problem, it will worsen and we will not be able to treat it in the future.

Research limits:

The limitations of this field research are as follows:

- Objective limits: This research deals with the issue of Internet addiction, through a questionnaire to elicit opinions, and an effort to find solutions or treatment for this problem.
- Spatial boundaries: This field research applied to a sample of ordinary Kuwaiti individuals in the State of Kuwait.
- Time limits: This research implemented in the academic year 2021/2022.

1-1 Internet Defining

We can define the Internet as follow: Widespread means of communication that connects millions of computers, and provides many services related to the provision of information. The Internet linguistically means the interconnection between networks scattered all over the world, and the interconnection and conversation of these devices is governing by a unified protocol called the Internet Communication Protocol. In addition, we can say Internet is about hundreds of millions of computers around the world connected to each other, and with the interconnectedness of this huge number of computers, e-mails can sent between them in the blink of an eye, in addition to exchanging files, still and moving images, and sounds. It agreed on a unified system for the exchange of all these types of information called the global fabric. Moreover, the process of linking through satellites as a better alternative than the phone that was used in the past. (Darwish 2016: 43-44).

1-2 Definition of addiction

Addiction in language: Continuing to do something or relying on it.

Idiomatically Addiction: Addiction defined in psychology and psychoanalysis as the habit of using certain substances or doing a specific activity for a long time with the intention of entering a state of euphoria and excluding sadness and depression. (Hamouda - 2015: 214)

Scientists differ in the definition of addiction, some consider it logical only on substances that a person may take and then cannot dispense with. But others consider this concept limited as they see that addiction is the inability of a person to dispense with something, regardless of This thing as long as it fulfills the rest of the conditions of addiction from the need for more of this thing on a continuous basis until it satisfies its need when it is deprived of it.

Addiction also defined as the continuous or periodic overuse of the addict's choice.

The World Health Organization in 1973 defined addiction as: "A psychological and sometimes organic condition that results from the organism's interaction with a drug or substance. Its characteristics include different responses and behavior patterns, always including an urgent desire to use or practice continuously or periodically, to feel its psychological effects." or to avoid the annoying effects that result from its unavailability.

According to the American Internet Addiction Association is "Internet use in excess of (38) hours per week without the need to work, with a tendency to increase the hours of use to satisfy desires. The same ones that were saturated with fewer hours, with psychological and physical symptoms when interrupted communication, including psychomotor tension, anxiety, and compulsively focusing on thinking about Internet. (Essam Mansour and Abdullah Al-Daboubi, 2011, 334).

In conclusion, addiction is the continuous use of certain substances or certain activities for a long time, and it is not limited to the use of certain substances, but includes other types of addiction other than drugs.

1-3 Definition of Internet Addiction:

Charlton (2002) defined it as a case of pathological and non-consensual use to the International Information Network (Internet), and lead to clinical disorders inferred; there are some manifestations such as tolerance and withdrawal symptoms. (Heba Bahei El Din Rabie, 2003, 557)

Baird and Wolf (2001) defined it as a state of lack of control and destructive use, for this technical method, the symptoms associated with it are similar to the pathological symptoms. Associated with pathological gambling. (Tahseen Bashir Mansour, 2004, p. 50)

1-4 Symptoms of Internet addict:

The Internet addict suffers from pain in the back and eyes and those dark circles around them. Obesity, wrist pain, lack of sleep, fatigue and exhaustion, which leads to inaction, going to work or school, neglecting his various duties, including family and academic duties, he is judged to be addicted if he exhibits the following behaviors:

1. Thirst for the Internet and neglect of social life and professional and professional obligations.
2. Spending sums due to the Internet from subscribing and purchasing various electronic tools...etc.
3. Neglecting the requirements of the family and feeling anxious and sad when there is a malfunction in the Internet, and neglecting his diet so that he eats his food while working on the Internet.
4. The user's denial of spending a long time on the network.
5. The individual is feeling that his life is not upright without the Internet. As indicated by the study conducted in World Mental Health Day that Internet users classified as addicts if they spend thirty hours and a half in front of the Internet per week.
6. Reducing the movement outside the house, and everything is worse than the one before it.
7. The inability to control the time the user spends on the Internet.
8. Access to the Internet, despite the fact that there is a lot of work that the user must accomplish.
9. The occurrence of some psychological withdrawal symptoms when reducing the use of the Internet for a period of time a month, such as distress or work to spoil a social, personal or professional relationship.

1-5 Effects of internet addiction:

Internet addiction has several effects, as follows:

1-5-1 Health effects:

- Damage to the eye because of radiation emitted by computer screens.
- Damage to hands from excessive use of the mouse.
- Damage to the ears of loudspeaker users.
- Damage to the spine and legs because of the type and duration of the session compared to computers.
- Associated damages such as obesity and the accompanying diseases it causes.

1-5-2 Psychological effects:

- Reducing the individual's ability to create a healthy psychological personality capable of interacting with society The reality is lived.
- Entering an alternate imaginary world provided by the Internet, which causes enormous psychological effects as it mixes up Reality is an illusion.

1-5-3 Social Effects:

- Family disintegration and rupture.
- A noticeable withdrawal of man from social interaction towards isolation.
- Loss of friends and weak family control over children.
- The impact on cultural identity, customs and values with this massive information invasion.

1-6 Internet addiction domains:

"Hardy" (2009) pointed: That the most attractive sites for Internet users are rooms chat, which takes up 35% of the time on the Internet, then searches the web it takes 7% of the time between research and information gathering, and according to studies in the field of the Internet, the most common areas used by Internet addicts are as follows:

1-6-1 Addiction of live chat rooms:

Online chat takes up a large amount of data packet exchanged between users of this global network, but that many users do not see in the Internet only a way to reach others. Online chatting lines may lead to addiction. "Maria Doron" sees that these people who use chat rooms are actually looking for social acceptance by others, while those who create characters other than their true character they are eager to be accepted as being themselves. (Al-Abaji Omar's).

1-6-2 Addiction to discussion clubs or forums:

They are special programs that work on the media site, or any other sites of a private nature, or public on the Internet, and allows the presentation of ideas and opinions in issues or topics for discussion on the site and opportunities for users reply and discuss.

1-6-3 Electronic game addiction:

Computer games give the person connected to the Internet like: (Ever Quest) or (PUBG) a feeling the hero for some players, which in turn causes bigger problems, the intense verbal properties give such games have a social dimension that does not exist in real life, and these qualities are described some players on online support groups are considered addicts. (Al-Abaji Omar Bashir's, 2007, 143)

1-6-4 Internet information addiction:

It is the gluttony in the search for information and the pursuit of finding it, and continuing to inspect the Internet to obtain information, that you do not use anymore or even seek to read statistics on (1000) people, from the United States, England, Germany, Singapore and Hong Kong. The statistics showed that about 50% of the research sample answered that they are personally Information addicts and 75% (of them) explained that computers, the Internet and information would become an addiction to many in the next century.

1-6-5 Pornography addiction:

Online pornographic websites are a form of organized crime carried out by local, regional and international networks that perform sexual performances psychologically and financially tempting through visible sites, or break into the e-mail of the Internet user without permission. Some French media consider the word "sex" to be the most common word used online. Norton was spotted in the period between February and in December, the word "sex" and its related vocabulary appeared at the top of the search list children on the Internet in the year 2009. Statistics in Algeria indicate that (63%) of teens use the Internet without their parents knowing what they are browsing, and are looking for Pornographic pages and images that display obscene images and teenagers fall into the abyss of entry it is based on curiosity, then falls into the trap of addiction to it, which affects their behavior. (Filali Rashid, 15, 2006)

1-6-6 gambling online:

Website addicts spend hours playing gambling or forbidden games on the Internet, for illicit gain, without getting bored.

1-6-7 online buying and selling

The obsession with buying and selling online, which affects some, as some people prefer daily for hours browsing online selling sites, and not wanting to buy them from the store.

General symptoms of internet addiction

Internet addicts suffer from general symptoms, including pain in the back and eyes, and those dark circles around them obesity, wrist pain, lack of sleep, fatigue and exhaustion, which leads to inaction going to work or school, neglecting his various duties, including family and academic duties, he is judged to be addicted if he exhibits the following behaviors:

- The user's denial of spending a long time on the network.
- Thirst for the Internet and neglect of social life and professional and professional obligations.

- The inability to control the time the user spends on the Internet.
- Neglecting the requirements of the family and feeling anxious and sad when there is a malfunction in the Internet and neglecting his diet so that he eats his food while working on the Internet.
- Spending sums due to the Internet from subscribing and purchasing various electronic tools...etc.
- The individual is feeling that his life is not upright without the Internet. As indicated by the study conducted in world Mental Health Day that Internet users classified as addicts if they spend thirty Hours and a half in front of the Internet per week.
- Reducing the movement outside the house, and everything is worse than the one before it.
- A month, such as distress or work to spoil a social, personal or professional relationship.
- Access to the Internet, despite the fact that there is a lot of work that the user must accomplish.
- The occurrence of some psychological withdrawal symptoms when reducing the use of the Internet for a period of time

1-7 Internet addiction diagnosis:

To diagnose Internet addiction, the Association for Psychology (A.P.A.) classified excessive use of the Internet as a disorder. If it impedes the person's normal life with the appearance of symptoms of the disorder. In addition, usually specialists use the same criteria of diagnosing other areas of addiction listed in the Fourth Diagnostic Statistical Manual (IV-DSM). In order for the person to be considered, an addict must have three or more of these things at any time during his use of the Internet over a period of twelve months. These criteria are as follows:

- Relapsing: The tendency to go back to the types of activities that were addictive to the individual and practice it.
- Conflict: It refers to the conflicts that take place between the addict and those around him such as interpersonal conflict, conflicts and inconsistencies between this activity and other activities others (work, social life, wishes and interests, and studies) or conflict that it takes place within the individual himself and is the psychological struggle related to this activity.
- Modification Mood: It refers to the subjective experience that he feels as a result to do this behavior. It is seen as a coping strategy in order to avoid the consequences of the lack of it accompanied by carrying or not accompanied.
- Salience: An individual's behavior is a salient characteristic, and this happens when this behavior is the most important and most valuable activity in an individual's life and controls his thinking and feelings significantly and excessive preoccupation, cognitive distortions, social behavior and feeling disorder eager to do this activity.
- Tolerance: The tendency to increase the hours of internet use to satisfy the desire itself, which is saturated by fewer hours.

1-8 Internet addiction treatment:

There are several ways to treat Internet addiction, including time management. In the case of severe addiction, time management is not sufficient. Rather, the patient must use the following effective methods:

- Finding external obstacles: setting an alarm before starting to enter the Internet, so that he intends to enter the Internet for one hour, for example.
- Do the opposite: if the patient, for example, used to use the Internet all days of the week, ask him to wait until he uses it on the weekend, and if he opens the email first thing when he wakes up, we ask him to wait until he finishes his breakfast.
- Determining the time of use: Reducing and regulating the hours of its use, so that if, for example, it enters for (40) hours per week, we ask him to reduce it to (20) hours per week. Organizing those hours and distributing them over the days of the week.
- Complete abstinence: As mentioned, the addiction of some patients is related to a specific field using the Internet. If the individual is addicted to live conversations, for example, we ask him to refrain from it completely, while we leave him free to use other things found in the Internet.
- Family therapy: Sometimes the whole family needs to receive treatment because
- Family problems caused by Internet addiction, so that a program developed to help restore discussion and dialogue among themselves and the family learns the danger of exceeding the reasonable limit in Internet use leads to addiction.

The conditions facing an Internet addict are radically different from drug addicts, yet some people use the Internet as a way to escape to their world, because in the real world they suffer from social isolation. Maybe we should think that we might be a reason to exclude some members of society to end up with addiction. Anything like Internet addiction.

2. DEDUCTIVE METHOD

A questionnaire on Internet addiction designed, consisting of three main axes, in addition to the basic data. These axes were as follows:

The first axis: Phenomenon diagnosis.

The second axis: Effects of Internet addiction.

The third axis: Internet addiction causes.

Of course, each of these three axes includes a set of questions, this questionnaire designed using the Microsoft Forms application, and the questionnaire link was <https://forms.office.com/r/YkAx8CrX7P>

As for the questionnaire questions, they were as follows:

Personal data:

- **Name:** (Optional)

- **Nationality:**

a) Kuwaiti

b) Non Kuwaiti

- **Type:**

a) Male

b) Female

- **Age:**

a) Less than 16 years.

b) From 16 to less than 20 years.

c) From 20 to less than 25 years.

d) From 25 to less than 30 years.

e) From 30 to less than 35 years.

f) From 35 to less than 40 years.

g) From 40 to less than 50 years.

h) From 50 to less than 65 years.

- **Job:**

a) Student.

b) Private sector.

c) Public sector.

d) Other.

- **Educational level:**

a) Less than university.

b) University.

c) More than university.

d) Other.

Questions: First Axis: Diagnosing the phenomenon:

- Are you wasting time from your work or study time because of using the internet?
 Yes No Possible
- Is using the internet taking up the time you are supposed to spend with your family?
 Yes No Possible
- Does excessive use of the internet affect your family life and cause disputes?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you lie to your family and friends about the number of hours you use the internet?
 Yes No Possible
- Can you stop using the internet without difficulty at any time you want?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you have a constant desire to use the internet in case you stop using it?
 Yes No Possible
- Does the internet and its uses keep you busy when you are with your family or friends?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you feel more self-centered and cared for when you use the internet?
 Yes No Possible
- Does internet use affect your sleep, eating, work or study times?
 Yes No Possible
- Is the first thing you think of when you wake up to use the internet and its applications?
 Yes No Possible
- Is the use of the internet reflected on your work life or study?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you feel remorse after using the internet for too long?
 Yes No Possible
- Does using the internet help you forget your problems and worries?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you appear as someone other than your normal self when using the internet?
 Yes No Possible
- Do family and private events reduce your use of the internet?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you feel that excessive use of the internet can destroy yourself?
 Yes No Possible
- Are you spending excessive amounts of money because of your frequent use of the internet?
 Yes No Possible

Questions: Third Axis: Internet addiction causes:

- Does the good financial situation contribute to the spread of the use of the internet?
 Yes No Possible
- Does emptiness and boredom contribute to the spread of internet use?
 Yes No Possible
- Does confidentiality in dealing while using the internet contribute to the increased use of it?
 Yes No Possible
- Do family problems increase the use of the internet to escape from these problems?
 Yes No Possible
- Does dependency, boredom, or annoyance make some people flee to the internet?
 Yes No Possible
- Does self-realization through social media programs contribute to the spread of internet use?
 Yes No Possible
- Does exposure to psychological trauma increase the use of the internet?
 Yes No Possible
- Does dazzle in games increase internet use?
 Yes No Possible
- Connecting with geographically distant friends increases the use of internet applications.
 Yes No Possible
- Parents neglecting their children and not monitoring them increases the rate of their use of the internet.
 Yes No Possible
- Do family problems increase the rate of internet use?
 Yes No Possible
- The lack of sports hobbies increases the rate of internet use.
 Yes No Possible
- Easy commerce (buying and selling) over the internet increases the rate of internet usage.
 Yes No Possible
- Are following stocks and gambling factors that increase the rate of internet use?
 Yes No Possible
- Does family distancing increase the rate of internet use?
 Yes No Possible
- Does the lack of religious scruples increase the rate of internet use, especially blocked sites?
 Yes No Possible

Questions: Second Axis: Effects of internet addiction:

- Is your weight gaining or losing significantly?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you feel a constant headache when using an internet application?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you feel back pain while using the internet?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you have trouble sleeping?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you sometimes feel blurred vision?
 Yes No Possible
- Are you moody?
 Yes No Possible
- Is your financial level affected by the internet and its applications?
 Yes No Possible
- Is time very important to you?
 Yes No Possible
- Are you an impulsive character?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you tend to isolate?
 Yes No Possible
- Are you worried about before?
 Yes No Possible
- Does most of your family use the internet a lot?
 Yes No Possible
- Are your lessons or work affected by the excessive use of the internet?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you feel you have a strong personality?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you feel like a relatively aggressive person?
 Yes No Possible
- Do you sometimes hide the websites you browse?
 Yes No Possible

Write your suggestions for treating the phenomenon of Internet addiction:

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Thank you for your cooperation with us to discuss this issue.

Mansour Mukhtar Ashkanani

Specialist coach (B) Deputy General Manager

Summary of survey results:

Variable	Category	Number	Percentage
Nationality	Kuwaiti	275	89.29%
	Non Kuwaiti	33	10.71%
Type	Male	165	53.57%
	Female	143	46.43%
Education Level	Less than University	11	3.57%
	University	55	17.86%
	Less than University	209	67.86%
	Other	33	10.71%
Age	Less than 20 years	11	3.57%
	From 20 to less than 25 years	10	3.25%
	From 25 to less than 30 years	9	2.92%
	From 30 to less than 35 years	13	4.22%
	From 35 to less than 40 years	15	4.87%
	From 40 to less than 45 years	53	17.21%
	From 45 to less than 50 years	61	19.81%
	From 50 to less than 65 years	48	15.58%
Job	Student	11	3.57%
	Private sector	55	17.86%
	Public sector	209	67.86%
	Other	33	10.71%
Total	308		

From the previous data, we note:

1. Most responses are Kuwaiti (89.29%).
2. Males represents (53.57%) which is greater than female by small values.
3. Most responses is in the age range from 40 and less than 45, and the range from 45 to less than 50, this is a very wrong, because we want approximately same numbers in all categories.
4. Most responses from workers in public sectors.

For the remaining questions in the questionnaire, the answers to them were as follows:

Pointer	Yes	No	Possible
<u>Questions: First Axis: Diagnosing the phenomenon:</u>			
Are you wasting time from your work or study time because of using the Internet?	132	121	55
Is using the internet taking up the time you are supposed to spend with your family?	187	77	88
Does excessive use of the Internet affect your family life and cause disputes?	132	132	44
Do you lie to your family and friends about the number of hours you use the Internet?	22	275	11
Can you stop using the Internet without difficulty at any time you want?	121	55	132
Do you have a constant desire to use the Internet in case you stop using it?	132	88	88
Does the Internet and its uses keep you busy when you are with your family or friends?	99	121	88
Do you feel more self-centered and cared for when you use the Internet?	66	165	77
Is the first thing you think of when you wake up to use the Internet and its applications?	88	165	55
Is the use of the Internet reflected on your work life or study?	143	99	66
Do you feel remorse after using the Internet for too long?	121	110	77
Does using the Internet help you forget your problems and worries?	22	154	132
Do you appear as someone other than your normal self when using the Internet?	0	231	77
Do family and private events reduce your use of the Internet?	165	77	66
Do you feel that excessive use of the Internet can destroy yourself?	121	132	55
Are you spending excessive amounts of money because of your frequent use of the Internet?	22	264	22
<u>Questions: Second Axis: Effects of internet addiction:</u>			
Is your weight gaining or losing significantly?	33	187	88
Do you feel a constant headache when using an Internet application?	77	165	66
Do you feel back pain while using the Internet?	110	99	99
Do you have trouble sleeping?	44	198	66
Do you sometimes feel blurred vision?	77	154	77
Are you moody?	77	187	44
Is your financial level affected by the Internet and its applications?	22	253	33
Is time very important to you?	253	22	33
Are you an impulsive character?	88	165	55
Do you tend to isolate?	33	198	77
Are you worried about before?	44	187	77
Does most of your family use the Internet a lot?	154	22	132
Do you feel you have a strong personality?	242	0	66
Do you feel like a relatively aggressive person?	0	297	11
Do you sometimes hide the websites you browse?	22	242	44
<u>Questions: Third Axis: Internet addiction causes:</u>			
Does the good financial situation contribute to the spread of the use of the Internet?	231	22	55
Does emptiness and boredom contribute to the spread of Internet use?	220	22	66
Does confidentiality in dealing while using the Internet contribute to the increased use of it?	121	88	99
Do family problems increase the use of the Internet to escape from these problems?	110	110	88
Does despondency, boredom, or annoyance make some people flee to the Internet?	154	66	88
Does self-realization through social media programs contribute to the spread of Internet use?	143	55	110
Does exposure to psychological trauma increase the use of the Internet?	110	77	121
Does dazzle in games increase internet use?	198	33	77
Connecting with geographically distant friends increases the use of Internet applications.	242	22	44
Parents neglecting their children and not monitoring them increases the rate of their use of the Internet.	231	33	44
Do family problems increase the rate of Internet use?	176	66	66
The lack of sports hobbies increases the rate of Internet use.	242	11	55
Easy commerce (buying and selling) over the Internet increases the rate of Internet usage.	275	0	33
Are following stocks and gambling factors that increase the rate of Internet use?	198	44	66
Does family distancing increase the rate of internet use?	231	22	55
Does the lack of religious scruples increase the rate of Internet use, especially blocked sites?	198	55	55

These are the main suggestions of those who responded to the survey:

- The lifestyle and lifestyle have made the internet a part of our daily life.
- Good time management is one of the most important solutions.
- Resorting to sports, engaging in crafts, learning new things, investing time in research and reading useful books.
- Distance from religion is the cause of most problems.
- Family disintegration is a major cause.

Analyze data using SPSS:

The following is the overall responses in SPSS File:

1 denotes to yes

2 denotes to No

3 denotes to Possible

The screenshot shows the IBM SPSS Statistics Data Editor interface. The main window displays a list of 33 questionnaire items (Number and Question) and their corresponding response data (1, 2, 3) for 310 variables. The data is organized in a grid format with columns for each variable and rows for each question. The status bar at the bottom indicates 'IBM SPSS Statistics Processor is ready' and 'Unicode ON'.

1- Questionnaire reliability coefficient:

By using SPSS software, we find questionnaire reliability coefficient is as follow:

Scale: ALL VARIABLES			
Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	308	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	308	100.0
a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.			
Reliability Statistics			
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items		
.882	47		

This value > 0.7, So this is an Excellent case

As previous questionnaire reliability coefficient equals (0.882), which refers to an excellent case.

2- Frequencies:

Frequency Table					
Are you wasting time from your work or study time because of using the Internet?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	84	27.3	27.3	27.3
	لا	112	36.4	36.4	63.6
	إلى حد ما	112	36.4	36.4	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Is using the internet taking up the time you are supposed to spend with your family?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	إلى حد ما	308	100.0	100.0	100.0

Does excessive use of the Internet affect your family life and cause disputes?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	152	49.4	49.4	49.4
	لا	44	14.3	14.3	63.6
	إلى حد ما	112	36.4	36.4	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Do you lie to your family and friends about the number of hours you use the Internet?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	22	7.1	7.1	7.1
	لا	154	50.0	50.0	57.1
	إلى حد ما	132	42.9	42.9	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Can you stop using the Internet without difficulty at any time you want?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	90	29.2	29.2	29.2
	لا	136	44.2	44.2	73.4
	إلى حد ما	82	26.6	26.6	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Do you have a constant desire to use the Internet in case you stop using it?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	168	54.5	54.5	54.5
	لا	132	42.9	42.9	97.4
	إلى حد ما	8	2.6	2.6	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Does the Internet and its uses keep you busy when you are with your family or friends?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	110	35.7	35.7	35.7
	لا	104	33.8	33.8	69.5
	إلى حد ما	94	30.5	30.5	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Do you feel more self-centered and cared for when you use the Internet?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	32	10.4	10.4	10.4
	لا	134	43.5	43.5	53.9
	إلى حد ما	142	46.1	46.1	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Is the use of the Internet reflected on your work life or study?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	56	18.2	18.2	18.2
	لا	186	60.4	60.4	78.6
	إلى حد ما	66	21.4	21.4	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Do you feel remorse after using the Internet for too long?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	88	28.6	28.6	28.6
	لا	214	69.5	69.5	98.1
	إلى حد ما	6	1.9	1.9	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Does using the Internet help you forget your problems and worries?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	162	52.6	52.6	52.6
	لا	64	20.8	20.8	73.4
	إلى حد ما	82	26.6	26.6	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Do you appear as someone other than your normal self when using the Internet?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	138	44.8	44.8	44.8
	لا	96	31.2	31.2	76.0
	إلى حد ما	74	24.0	24.0	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Do family and private events reduce your use of the Internet?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	160	51.9	51.9	51.9
	لا	92	29.9	29.9	81.8
	إلى حد ما	56	18.2	18.2	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Do you feel that excessive use of the Internet can destroy yourself?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	118	38.3	38.3	38.3
	لا	190	61.7	61.7	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Are you spending excessive amounts of money because of your frequent use of the Internet?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	140	45.5	45.5	45.5
	لا	134	43.5	43.5	89.0
	إلى حد ما	34	11.0	11.0	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Is your weight gaining or losing significantly?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	194	63.0	63.0	63.0
	لا	114	37.0	37.0	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Do you feel a constant headache when using an Internet application?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	242	78.6	78.6	78.6
	لا	24	7.8	7.8	86.4
	إلى حد ما	42	13.6	13.6	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Do you feel back pain while using the Internet?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	118	38.3	38.3	38.3
	لا	152	49.4	49.4	87.7
	إلى حد ما	38	12.3	12.3	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Do you have trouble sleeping?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	130	42.2	42.2	42.2
	لا	102	33.1	33.1	75.3
	إلى حد ما	76	24.7	24.7	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Do you sometimes feel blurred vision?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	182	59.1	59.1	59.1
	لا	96	31.2	31.2	90.3
	إلى حد ما	30	9.7	9.7	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Are you moody?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	230	74.7	74.7	74.7
	لا	66	21.4	21.4	96.1
	إلى حد ما	12	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Is your financial level affected by the Internet and its applications?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	92	29.9	29.9	29.9
	لا	70	22.7	22.7	52.6
	إلى حد ما	146	47.4	47.4	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Is time very important to you?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	170	55.2	55.2	55.2
	لا	138	44.8	44.8	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Are you an impulsive character?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	160	51.9	51.9	51.9
	لا	78	25.3	25.3	77.3
	إلى حد ما	70	22.7	22.7	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Do you tend to isolate?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	200	64.9	64.9	64.9
	لا	42	13.6	13.6	78.6
	إلى حد ما	66	21.4	21.4	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Are you worried about before?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	208	67.5	67.5	67.5
	لا	68	22.1	22.1	89.6
	إلى حد ما	32	10.4	10.4	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Does most of your family use the Internet a lot?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	76	24.7	24.7	24.7
	لا	172	55.8	55.8	80.5
	إلى حد ما	60	19.5	19.5	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Do you feel you have a strong personality?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	84	27.3	27.3	27.3
	لا	112	36.4	36.4	63.6
	إلى حد ما	112	36.4	36.4	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Do you feel like a relatively aggressive person?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	إلى حد ما	308	100.0	100.0	100.0

Do you sometimes hide the websites you browse?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	152	49.4	49.4	49.4
	لا	44	14.3	14.3	63.6
	إلى حد ما	112	36.4	36.4	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Does the good financial situation contribute to the spread of the use of the Internet?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	22	7.1	7.1	7.1
	لا	154	50.0	50.0	57.1
	إلى حد ما	132	42.9	42.9	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Does emptiness and boredom contribute to the spread of Internet use?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	90	29.2	29.2	29.2
	لا	136	44.2	44.2	73.4
	إلى حد ما	82	26.6	26.6	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Does confidentiality in dealing while using the Internet contribute to the increased use of it?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	168	54.5	54.5	54.5
	لا	132	42.9	42.9	97.4
	إلى حد ما	8	2.6	2.6	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Do family problems increase the use of the Internet to escape from these problems?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	110	35.7	35.7	35.7
	لا	104	33.8	33.8	69.5
	إلى حد ما	94	30.5	30.5	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Does despondency, boredom, or annoyance make some people flee to the Internet?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	32	10.4	10.4	10.4
	لا	134	43.5	43.5	53.9
	إلى حد ما	142	46.1	46.1	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Does self-realization through social media programs contribute to the spread of Internet use?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	144	46.8	46.8	46.8
	لا	122	39.6	39.6	86.4
	إلى حد ما	42	13.6	13.6	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Does exposure to psychological trauma increase the use of the Internet?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	56	18.2	18.2	18.2
	لا	186	60.4	60.4	78.6
	إلى حد ما	66	21.4	21.4	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Does dazzle in games increase internet use?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	88	28.6	28.6	28.6
	لا	214	69.5	69.5	98.1
	إلى حد ما	6	1.9	1.9	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Connecting with geographically distant friends increases the use of Internet applications.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	162	52.6	52.6	52.6
	لا	64	20.8	20.8	73.4
	إلى حد ما	82	26.6	26.6	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Parents neglecting their children and not monitoring them increases the rate of their use of the Internet.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	138	44.8	44.8	44.8
	لا	96	31.2	31.2	76.0
	إلى حد ما	74	24.0	24.0	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Do family problems increase the rate of Internet use?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	نعم	160	51.9	51.9	51.9
	لا	92	29.9	29.9	81.8
	إلى حد ما	56	18.2	18.2	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

The lack of sports hobbies increases the rate of Internet use.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid نعم	118	38.3	38.3	38.3
لا	190	61.7	61.7	100.0
Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Easy commerce (buying and selling) over the Internet increases the rate of Internet usage.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid نعم	140	45.5	45.5	45.5
لا	134	43.5	43.5	89.0
إلى حد ما	34	11.0	11.0	100.0
Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Are following stocks and gambling factors that increase the rate of Internet use?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid نعم	194	63.0	63.0	63.0
لا	114	37.0	37.0	100.0
Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Does family distancing increase the rate of internet use?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid نعم	242	78.6	78.6	78.6
لا	24	7.8	7.8	86.4
إلى حد ما	42	13.6	13.6	100.0
Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Does the lack of religious scruples increase the rate of Internet use, especially blocked sites?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid نعم	118	38.3	38.3	38.3
لا	152	49.4	49.4	87.7
إلى حد ما	38	12.3	12.3	100.0
Total	308	100.0	100.0	

3- Descriptive values:

Descriptive Statistics				
No.	Question	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Are you wasting time from your work or study time because of using the Internet?	308	2.09	0.794
2	Is using the internet taking up the time you are supposed to spend with your family?	308	3.00	0.000
3	Does excessive use of the Internet affect your family life and cause disputes?	308	1.87	0.918
4	Do you lie to your family and friends about the number of hours you use the Internet?	308	2.36	0.611
5	Can you stop using the Internet without difficulty at any time you want?	308	1.97	0.748
6	Do you have a constant desire to use the Internet in case you stop using it?	308	1.48	0.550
7	Does the Internet and its uses keep you busy when you are with your family or friends?	308	1.95	0.814
8	Do you feel more self-centered and cared for when you use the Internet?	308	2.36	0.662
9	Is the first thing you think of when you wake up to use the Internet and its applications?	308	1.67	0.704
10	Is the use of the Internet reflected on your work life or study?	308	2.03	0.630
11	Do you feel remorse after using the Internet for too long?	308	1.73	0.485
12	Does using the Internet help you forget your problems and worries?	308	1.74	0.853
13	Do you appear as someone other than your normal self when using the Internet?	308	1.79	0.805
14	Do family and private events reduce your use of the Internet?	308	1.66	0.768
15	Do you feel that excessive use of the Internet can destroy yourself?	308	1.62	0.487
16	Are you spending excessive amounts of money because of your frequent use of the Internet?	308	1.66	0.669
17	Is your weight gaining or losing significantly?	308	1.37	0.484
18	Do you feel a constant headache when using an Internet application?	308	1.35	0.709
19	Do you feel back pain while using the Internet?	308	1.74	0.664
20	Do you have trouble sleeping?	308	1.82	0.800
21	Do you sometimes feel blurred vision?	308	1.51	0.668
22	Are you moody?	308	1.29	0.534

23	Is your financial level affected by the Internet and its applications?	308	2.18	0.863
24	Is time very important to you?	308	1.45	0.498
25	Are you an impulsive character?	308	1.71	0.815
26	Do you tend to isolate?	308	1.56	0.823
27	Are you worried about before?	308	1.43	0.674
28	Does most of your family use the Internet a lot?	308	1.95	0.664
29	Do you feel you have a strong personality?	308	2.09	0.794
30	Do you feel like a relatively aggressive person?	308	3.00	0.000
31	Do you sometimes hide the websites you browse?	308	1.87	0.918
32	Does the good financial situation contribute to the spread of the use of the Internet?	308	2.36	0.611
33	Does emptiness and boredom contribute to the spread of Internet use?	308	1.97	0.748
34	Does confidentiality in dealing while using the Internet contribute to the increased use of it?	308	1.48	0.550
35	Do family problems increase the use of the Internet to escape from these problems?	308	1.95	0.814
36	Does despondency, boredom, or annoyance make some people flee to the Internet?	308	2.36	0.662
37	Does self-realization through social media programs contribute to the spread of Internet use?	308	1.67	0.704
38	Does exposure to psychological trauma increase the use of the Internet?	308	2.03	0.630
39	Does dazzle in games increase Internet use?	308	1.73	0.485
40	Connecting with geographically distant friends increases the use of Internet applications.	308	1.74	0.853
41	Parents neglecting their children and not monitoring them increases the rate of their use of the Internet.	308	1.79	0.805
42	Do family problems increase the rate of Internet use?	308	1.66	0.768
43	The lack of sports hobbies increases the rate of Internet use.	308	1.62	0.487
44	Easy commerce (buying and selling) over the Internet increases the rate of Internet use.	308	1.66	0.669
45	Are following stocks and gambling factors that increase the rate of Internet use?	308	1.37	0.484
46	Does family distancing increase the rate of Internet use?	308	1.35	0.709
47	Does the lack of religious scruples increase the rate of Internet use, especially blocked schools?	308	1.74	0.664
	Valid N (listwise)	308		

3. RESEARCH ANALYSIS

From Microsoft forms results and SPSS analysis we find:

There is excessive use of the Internet, which reflected in family relationships (60.7%), study (46.26%), as well as work (41.16%). Individuals have become unable to do without the Internet.

The results also showed that the process of using the Internet has negative and health effects, such as back pain, eyes, and a tendency to isolate greatly (50%), as well, and it is strange that the large percentage of responses indicate attention to time and its importance (82.14%), which contradicts their answers to the rest of the questions.

The results also indicated that the most important causes of Internet addiction are:

- Emptiness and boredom when many.
- Confidentiality in dealing while using the Internet.
- Family problems and troubles.
- Hopelessness, boredom, or annoyance.
- Self-realization through social media programs.
- Exposure to psychological trauma.
- Dazzling in gaming software
- Ease of communication with geographically distant friends.
- Parents neglect of children and lack of supervision.
- No sports hobbies.
- Easy trading (buying and selling) online.
- Follow stocks and gambles.

We can also identify the causes of Internet addiction as follows:

- The lack of emotional support in adolescents causes them to chase after illusory gratification and temporary pleasure by chatting with strangers.
- Unlocking and expressing hidden desires through chat rooms that provide young people with an excellent opportunity to get rid of strict societal restrictions.
- Chat rooms provide a means for emotional emptying and unloading shipments of anger, repression and aggression. Therefore, these rooms become the safe haven and the greatest savior, for the self-repression of unconsciousness and confidence, which leads to the illusion of intimacy and familiarity.
- The individual tries, through the Internet, to get rid of psychological anxiety and the stresses of daily life.
- The spread of Internet cafes and the availability of financial liquidity for adolescents.
- Being influenced by other cultures, especially in the era of tremendous development in communications.
- The negative concept of urbanization and temptation. (Hamouda - 2015 - 217)
- Easy access to computers and mobiles that enable young people to use the Internet.
- The large number of Internet providers in the country and their competition with each other.
- The void and family disintegration that lead to the delinquency of some adolescents.
- The family's lack of interest in its children leads to many problems, the simplest of which is Internet addiction.
- Not to put restrictions in the software that limit the use of some of them unless the person exceeds a specific age.
- Lack of religious faith.

4. CONCLUSION

We conclude from the foregoing that the concept of Internet addiction has recently emerged and that the symptoms of this addiction vary between psychological and physiological symptoms. Reality is one of the most important causes of an individual's addiction to the Internet, and of course, the type of treatment varies according to the personality of the addict and the quality of his addiction.

We can say that Internet addiction is growing rapidly even without formal recognition as a separate and distinct behavioral addiction and with continuing disagreement over diagnostic criteria. Therefore, more research must be done to prove this phenomenon and to propose methods of treatment.

In addition, in the end we must reconnect the social relationships that have been broken or nearly broken, due to our closing ourselves in the virtual world. For example, we can reconnect with friends whom we have not seen in a while and have not gone out with them, and ask about our relatives whom we have not seen in a while.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

These tips to contribute to reducing the problem of addiction to social networking sites:

- Calculate your access periods to applications: There are many applications that calculate the time you enter and exit the application, these applications help you to know the most applications that waste your time in order to avoid them.
- Organize your time: Set yourself life rules in dealing with your time, the void always makes you subconsciously hold the mobile and browse as many applications as possible. Therefore, I always advise that you have a specific time to access these sites. In addition, that it be in a disciplined time after completing all your basic and important work. It is also important to put rest periods so as not to disturb your eyes with the rays of mobile phones and electronic devices, and to relax your body after a long period of browsing and sitting.
- Don't follow unimportant people: Always try to stop following unimportant people and those who do not add much to your information and waste your time, especially in video applications, the more updates with these people increase your time and browsing, just try to add those who have an advantage in news and activities and benefit from them in your life.

- Take a break from social contact: It is useful to set breaks and days without the Internet; this gradually helps you to deal with the Internet independently and increases your ability to control it and not become addictive.
- Set a specific time to spend on the Internet and make sure that it does not exceed three hours per day.
- Make sure to exercise outside the house.
- Do not neglect the daily problems and your social relationships.
- Avoid using the internet without a specific purpose.
- Do one of your favorite hobbies.
- Increase family closeness,
- More moral and religious commitment.

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